

THE MIXED METHODS IN TEACHING: ROLE OF BELIEFS

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Abstract. This article discusses the importance of mixed methods and the role of beliefs in teaching foreign languages, especially English, to students majoring in non-philological disciplines. In particular, important aspects of the formation of English language knowledge and skills in students studying in non-philological specialties through independent learning technology were analyzed. The tasks, mechanisms and effectiveness of independent learning technology in foreign language teaching were studied and appropriate recommendations were made.

Keywords: Self-study technology, students of non-philological education, creative thinking, methods, discussion, system of education.

СМЕШАННЫЕ МЕТОДЫ В ОБУЧЕНИИ: РОЛЬ УБЕЖДЕНИЙ

Аннотация. В этой статье обсуждается важность смешанных методов и роль убеждений в обучении иностранным языкам, особенно английскому, студентам, специализирующимся на нефилологических дисциплинах. В частности, были проанализированы важные аспекты формирования знаний и умений английского языка у студентов, обучающихся по нефилологическим специальностям, с помощью технологии самостоятельного обучения. Были изучены задачи, механизмы и эффективность технологии самостоятельного обучения в преподавании иностранного языка и даны соответствующие рекомендации.

Ключевые слова: Технология самообучения, студенты нефилологического образования, творческое мышление, методы, дискуссия, система образования.

INTRODUCTION (KIRISH)

However, despite the central status of the word among linguistic units and its mental reality for speakers, as a result of which they do not experience serious difficulties in isolating and identifying words in the flow of speech, it is incredibly difficult to define a word. Currently, there are many definitions, among them there are many proposed by linguists working on the material of the English language, but there is not a single generally recognized and universal one.

LITERATURE REVIEW (MAVZUGA OID ADABIYOTLARNING TAHLILI)

In the register of lexical units, the most significant role belongs to the word. It is not by chance, the human language is often called the language of words: after all, it is the words, in their totality, as the vocabulary of the language, that are the building material without which no language is inconceivable; and it is the words that change and are combined in coherent speech according to the laws of the grammatical structure of a given language. Thus, the word acts as a necessary unit of the language both in the field of vocabulary (vocabulary) and in the field of grammar (grammatical structure), and therefore the word should be generally recognized as the main language unit: all other units of the language (for example, morphemes, phraseological units, any grammatical constructions) are somehow conditioned by the presence of words and, therefore, presuppose the existence of such a unit as the word.

Foreign language teaching methodology as a science has a history of more than 200 years. This is the period to observe different attitudes towards foreign language teaching methods

possible. One such view belongs to academician L.V. Shcherba¹. According to him, despite the fact that the methodology of teaching any science is a science, is not considered a theoretical science. It solves practical problems, including foreign languages.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY (TADQIQOT METODOLOGIYASI)

The teaching methodology is not only based on the evidence of psychology, but also general and based on private linguistic research. A linguistic linguistic phenomenon. This is the methodology if it deals with the laws of origin and motion what to do to put into practice the necessary linguistic phenomenon based on the laws answers the question of whether. The most valuable of the methodological books also written by linguists.

The statement of knowledge is considered to be the main goal of education of this method the basic principles are:

1. Language learning is based on written speech.
2. Grammar is taken as a subject of study, and vocabulary is subordinated to it selected. Grammar exercises were the main method of work.
3. First, the grammatical rule is memorized, and then make sentences based on the rules recommended.
4. Grammatical form and meaning of words by word-for-word translation explained.
5. Language material is mastered by word-for-word translation and dry memorization.
6. It is limited to memorizing words out of context, alone.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS (TAHLIL VA NATIJALAR)

Different versions of this method are known historically. They can be divided into two major groups: natural and direct methods. In the natural method. Learning a foreign language should be in line with the conditions of mastering the native language. Methods' main goal is to learn to read and write by learning to speak a foreign language. The idea that it is possible to get is formed for practical purposes. Natural The most important of the principles included in the method is to create a language environment. There are different approaches to the practical application of the proposed methodological principles. This can be clearly seen in the creative work of the representatives of the method. In the new interpretation of the goal of foreign language education, based on the results of pragmatic linguistic research. This branch of linguistics interprets language as a sphere of human activity, not a system of linguistic forms. New findings in the field of language education that have been accumulated since the early 1970s. The set has led to heated debates in the field of educational goals. The purpose of defining the main directions of foreign language teaching is to teach students. "Behavioral Training" were adopted. In the 70s, "communicative method has been proven in several stages after a series of attempts.

CONCLUSION

As a result, students only passively accept language knowledge and their motivation to learn is stifled. The third problem is that roles of teachers and students are not appropriate, teacher play the role of instructor in the classroom, and rarely explains language learning strategies, leaving the important task of learning vocabulary after class. These teaching problems cause students to memorize vocabulary books or vocabulary lists mechanically, and they always forget old words after learning new words, therefore, it is difficult to expand the breadth of the vocabulary.

^{1/17} M.Xodjayev, M.Qahhorova "Chet til o;qitish metodikasi" – T: Fan va texnologiyalar, 2012.

In addition, students lack the depth of vocabulary learning, and only master the literal meaning of the words they learn, but do not really master the dynamics of the semantics in the context. As a result, students are bored with vocabulary learning and feel that vocabulary learning is boring, resulting in poor speaking and writing ability (productive ability), as well as some common problems in class and examinations, such as, poor semantic flow and inaccurate collocation or word selection.

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